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Vision of a
Virtual Infrastructure for Storing and Processing Scientific Data

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ABSTRACT

Current and future scientific instruments generate vast amounts of data that require advanced means to store and process them by world-wide collaborations. By studying different use cases, we found that, albeit significant advances in distributed research infrastructures were made over the last decade, scientists still struggle with manually operating their virtual data infrastructure, being limited in collaborating with other scientists, and lacking easy means to quickly adopt emerging computing technologies. In this “work in progress”, we present three scientific case studies, evaluate existing technologies for data management and propose a flexible yet simple to use conceptual framework for organizing data in distributed, heterogeneous, collaborative environments. Our vision is that scientists declaratively define their virtual data infrastructure, leaving the task of implementing it to a runtime system that compiles, enacts and monitors the necessary data management operations.

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INTRODUCTION

Facing the *data tsunami*, in the foreword to [13], Neelie Kroes (Vice-President of the European Commission, responsible for the Digital Agenda) states: “Scientists should be able to concentrate on the best ways to make use of data. Data become an infrastructure that scientists can use on their way to new frontiers.”, and Hey et al. [12] postulate the forth paradigm for science: *data-intensive scientific discovery*.

Facilitating that vision requires significant technological advances and common data services [17] to manage the whole life cycle of data from its initial creation to its analysis and its preservation [4]. State-of-the-Art scientific research requires profound collaborations sharing and combining data, tools and resources. In our case studies, we also observed the need for seamless integration of emerging technologies such as Cloud computing or Map-Reduce [6] and existing e-Science infrastructures based on Grid computing. We find that solutions for Grid computing establish two extremes: Well-known toolkits such as Globus [11], UNICORE [27] and gLite [8] provide low-level interfaces and may be adapted to different scientific domains; Domain-specific portals and clients such as the Collaborative Climate Community Data and Processing Grid (C3Grid) for the climate community [5] and TextGridLab in the field of Digital Humanities [25] provide comfortable, high-level interfaces.

Even if scientists are capable to efficiently use all these solutions for processing their data, they struggle in maintaining the big picture. The main reason for this is the lack of means to manage metadata independently of the used technologies and infrastructures. At best each infrastructure provides an *isolated* view of the data stored and processed with it. Crossing borders of infrastructures – to make use of the best ways to process the data or simply to collaborate with other scientists – creates isolated chunks of data.

Therefore, we aim at a framework that lets scientists easily and flexibly declare how their virtual infrastructure for storing and processing data (VISPA) is composed. Simplicity is achieved by letting scientists *declare* how the infrastructure is structured – opposed to, often manually, executing various data management operations. In our framework, the VISPA runtime will compile, enact and monitor these operations. For each type of infrastructure, the compiler will take their capabilities into account.

The basic unit for managing data is a *view* which encapsulates data in a specific context. Virtually, a view can hold any type and size of data. For example, it might be a single value of a huge table in a relational database, the whole database or a file generated out of this database. Thinking vice versa, a view could be a file containing results of a scientific simulation, it could be a single line extracted from that file or a transformation into a table of a database. The actual incarnation of data only depends on what is best suited to a scientist’s needs and the capabilities of the used infrastructure. Scientists could model their data bottom-up, top-down or beginning at the desired level of abstraction. Arbitrary metadata may be attached to any view. Views may be linked with each other to capture provenance information.

The framework will support three different modi operandi:

Exclusive Every operation on the data *must* be declared through the framework, eg by using a GUI for defining the views.

Descriptive The framework is used to describe data that already exists or will exist but *no data operations* are enacted. Scientists may use the framework for monitoring the state of the virtual data infrastructure.

Hybrid The virtual data infrastructure contains views that are managed by the VISPA runtime and those that are only described.

Paper Outline

In Chapter 2, we present three case studies from different scientific domains. Chapter 3 describes existing technologies for storing and processing data. Chapter 4 introduces our concept for a view-based framework. Examples for using views with the framework are demonstrated in Chapter 5. We present our conclusions in Chapter 6.

CASE STUDIES

We present three case studies illustrating data management operations in different scientific domains.

2.1 DISTRIBUTED WORKFLOWS

Constrained Local Universe Simulations (CLUES) are created through a relatively small semi-automatic workflow (cf. Figure 1). Due to their high memory requirements the simulations are run on remote HPC resources. During each simulation several snapshots are recorded and stored for further post-processing.

Figure 1: CLUES workflow.

Today, most data management operations in the CLUES workflow [10] are **manually** performed by the scientists. This results from the following four observations:

1. the involvement of several scientists from different institutes,

2. the distributed processing of simulations at HPC centers, NASA¹, NIC², LRZ³, BSC⁴,
3. the distributed storage of significant amounts of data products (on tape and online systems at the HPC centers as well as systems at the home institute of the scientists), *and*
4. subsequent post-processing steps (on local systems and HPC centers).

The data product for a complete simulation consists of 120-150 snapshots each approx. 6.1 TB in size. Simply copying it around over slow, congested or expensive network links is not appropriate. Collection of all data in one (or more) storage centers is required which should additionally provide special resources for post-processing.

Producing a video of the formation of a galaxy may require special hardware and software for efficient rendering. Hence, the snapshots need to be transferred to sites providing these resources. However, a video may not need all information stored in a snapshot. Other post-processing methods such as *Halo Finder*, *Merger Trees*, *Halo Tracer*, etc. do not need special hardware, but may benefit from emerging data-intensive programming models (Map-Reduce) which require the data stored in specific file systems.

Figure 2: Parameter sweep simulation that is steered from a PC. Simulations are executed on one or more multi-core servers. The input data is fetched from a storage server to which the raw results are uploaded.

2.2 DISTRIBUTED PARAMETER SWEEP STUDY

Parameter sweep studies (PSS) usually involve data sets to be analyzed and a large number of parameter set instances. Often scientists use their personal computer (workstation or laptop) to coordinate the execution of the PSS and

¹ NASA Ames Research Center, CA, USA
² John von Neumann Institute for Computing, Jülich, Germany
³ Leibniz Rechenzentrum Garching, Germany
⁴ Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain

to process the results. For actual processing parallel machines (local or remote SMPs or clusters) and available Grid infrastructure are used. Hence, already in the simplest case, data resides on distributed resources. Often, the scenario gets suddenly complicated, for example by unavailable processing resources, required partial re-runs or exchange with other researchers, and requires additional data operations to maintain the desired progress of the study and – at the same time – ensure scientific standards (ie reproducibility).

Figure 2 illustrates the basic scenario in more detail. The main compute resources are a personal computer (PC), a set of multi-core servers (SMP) and a storage which holds both the data to be analyzed and the obtained raw data results. The PC is used for creating the configurations of the experiments and analyzing the validated results. The SMP (or cluster) is used for executing the experiments, validating their results and rerunning experiments if necessary.

Figure 3: File spaces and their integration into existing local and remote compute resources at AWI.

2.3 FILE SPACES, ARCHIVING AND COLLABORATION

Figure 3 illustrates the environment components for managing scientific data at the *Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research* (AWI). The environment distinguishes three main levels in the data infrastructure named “personal”, “group”, and “archive” with different integration into compute resources and metadata policies resulting from different purposes. The *personal* space serves for individual ongoing data processing, the file space *group* allows data sharing at the level of working groups or interdisciplinary projects, and *archive* is the space for long term archiving. Data of the personal and group space may be mounted for read and write access at desktops, mounted for read access at servers, written via FTP or SCP from servers, and accessed via FTP or SCP from clusters at AWI. The data backend is provided by SAM-FS. AWI scientists may access their data from external clusters via an SSH gateway. Publishing and archiving functionality is provided by the information system PANGAEA [16]. The data publication workflow for PANGAEA involves documentation of data by metadata and quality checks. Data curators enforce institute policies for metadata. Collaboration with external partners – specifically, the exchange of data sets – is implemented through an FTP server.

2.4 DISCUSSION OF THE CASE STUDIES

Today, scientists being involved in the above case studies have to decide themselves about the resources to be used and to issue the necessary data transfers manually for managing their own data or cooperating with external partners. Moreover, most of the metadata describing the handling of the data is not “digitally” available to automate data management or to easily reproduce research results.

Albeit the use cases share common data operations such as copying and transforming data, the overall data management workflows differ. Also, scientists often use execution environments providing different interfaces such as NFS, SAMBA, FTP, SCP, GridFTP and Web portals to access the data. Moreover, scientists face difficulties in knowing what data management methods are available at a target resource, particularly if suddenly unavailable resources need to be replaced by others.

We argue that scientists already construct virtual data infrastructures in their heads or on paper, but lack methods to make these blue prints available for systematic and automatic evaluation by computers.

Popular Grid computing toolkits such as Globus [11], UNICORE [27] and gLite [8] provide basic tools for transferring files (GridFTP, `ucc *-file1` and `glite-transfer-*`) and logical namespaces for files, particularly, to enable transparent management of storage locations for replicas. However, support for user-defined metadata is not fully implemented. The Globus Replica Location Service (RLS) allows to attach arbitrary metadata to a data object. However, the RLS's metadata query interface allows basic filter operations only. UNICORE does not provide means for attaching any metadata to files. While the gLite File Catalogue lets users associate a single character string as metadata to a logical file name (LFN), it does not provide means to query that information. On the other hand, it does provide rich capabilities to set access control list-based file permissions.

Several domain-specific systems have been developed that address some of the shortcomings of the above systems. MyLEAD [18] extends the Globus metadata catalog to let geo scientists explore vast amounts of atmospheric data. For the climate community, the Generation N Data Management System [9] extends Globus to implement workspaces and timely provisioning of data that is negotiated by a broker. The architecture for *Data mining and integration* (DMI) [3] supports the execution of DMI processes on heterogeneous resources. Particularly, the DMI architecture defines a DMI language that allows the composition of a *data-flow*. DataFinder [22] is interfaced with UNICORE to enable data structuring and metadata management.

Systems specifically designed to manage data often provide more rich feature sets for comfortable, flexible and extensible handling of data and metadata. Prominent examples are OGSA-DAI² [1] and iRODS³ [19]. OGSA-DAI was originally developed to enable access to remote databases by combining Grid and web service technologies. Because it integrates standard tools for querying relational and XML databases, it enables rich applications managing metadata. In contrast, iRODS manages large sets of files and lets users associate arbitrary metadata with individual files. The metadata is stored in relational databases enabling SQL-like queries. Furthermore, data management operations may be described by rules that utilize so-called micro-services.

In the fields of Arts and Humanities, data products and their relationships are managed through *digital repositories* [2, 20]. The emphasis of such repositories is on modeling the semantics of data and curating research results. Federating repositories enables global collaborations and interdisciplinary exchange.

At institute level, distributed file systems such as the network file system (NFS) [21] enable access to files from different computers and also the easy sharing of files among users. In high-performance computing systems, parallel file systems such as Lustre [23] and Ceph [29] provide fast access to data.

¹ Unicore Commandline Client

² Open Grid Services Architecture - Data Access and Integration

³ integrated Rule-Oriented Data System

Wide-area network file systems such as XtremFS [14] must cope with slow or unreliable components causing excess delays or network partitioning. More recent file systems, eg, XtremFS, also support arbitrary metadata and integrate various mechanisms for specifying file access permissions.

DISCUSSION

Within their limited system scopes the above presented approaches provide important and reasonable solutions. However, scientists find it difficult to cross system borders, that is, for example, using both Grid-enabled remote resources and traditional local clusters. Emerging technologies such as Cloud computing further complicate such scenarios. The difficulties arise from the differing interfaces to access the data resources and the expectations of the scientists for unified methods, further complicated by the fact that metadata may only be stored within the respective (isolated) domain/resource. Generic APIs such as JavaGAT [28] and SAGA [15] may mitigate differences in interfaces. Still, the challenge to integrate isolated metadata persists.

CONCEPT OF VIEWS

We present the main aspects of views, how they are declaratively described and how they are managed at runtime.

4.1 MAIN ASPECTS OF VIEWS

A view encapsulates data in a specific context, which is defined by different categories: metadata (core and user defined), provenance, content, permissions, technology and resource mapping. Views are addressable (by unique identifiers) and stateful. Their life cycle may involve time periods when they are inactive or active. Figure 4 illustrates the possible states and allowed state changes.

Figure 4: Life cycle of a view. Each view begins in the state declared and ends in the state cleanup.

The state changes are as follows:

- ① If a declared view contains all metadata necessary for provisioning the data, its state becomes complete.
- ② If a declared view lacks information for its provisioning, its state is incomplete.
- ③ If the missing information of a view were provided, it becomes complete.
- ④ The runtime system compiles the necessary operations and enacts them for provisioning the data.
- ⑤ When the desired access time period is reached, the view is said to be active.
- ⑥ When the desired access time period is not reached yet, the view remains inactive.
- ⑦ If the current access period expires and a subsequent one follows, the view switches into the state inactive. Similarly, if another access period begins, the view changes into the state active.
- ⑧ Once the last active period has expired or the user cancels the view, the view changes to the state terminated.
- ⑨ When a view is not needed anymore, it is canceled.
- ⑩ The storage used by terminated views is freed. All the metadata, however, is kept and may be used for subsequent processing.

4.2 DECLARATIVE DESCRIPTION OF A VIEW'S CONTENT

Besides offering technology- and location-independent management for scientific data, our approach simplifies data management by letting users **declaratively** describing their data infrastructure. Already in the 1970ies, Shu et al. [24] developed EXPRESS to explore the idea of using high-level nonprocedural languages for defining data (DEFINE) and for data restructuring (CONVERT).

The runtime system compares the current state of the data infrastructure with the described target and compiles necessary operations to maintain the desired data accessibility.

Figure 5: Overview of the main categories for declaratively describing views.

Figure 5 illustrates the different categories to describe a view. A description of a view answers the four main questions:

- What is the content of a view?
- Who may access the data?
- How is the data accessed?
- When and where needs the data be accessible?

Answering the first question, provides the core metadata of a view (category *Metadata/Core*). These contain a unique identifier (id), the status and the view's creation time (ctime). The unique identifier is calculated as a hash of the full description of a view.

Updates to the description of a view (in any subset of all categories) may be handled in two different ways. The first variant does not allow any update to the description once the view is handed over to the *View Description Store* which puts it into the state declared. Practically, this means, that any update to its description requires to create another view that names the to be changed view as its source (cf. category *Provenance*). The second approach employs versioning to maintain older versions of a view. Which approach provides more easy to maintain and understand semantics need to be validated with a prototype.

Users may add any metadata to view (category *Metadata/User*). Relationships among views are described by naming all sources using their unique

identifiers (category *Provenance*). The actual content of a view may be described by using various *built-in* operators or user-defined functions (UDF) that use the content of source views as input (cf. category *Provenance*). Table 1 lists important operators and describes their semantics.

Table 1: Built-in operators for defining the content of a view.

Operator	Description
register	The views purpose is to integrate the data represented by the location into the virtual data infrastructure.
metadata	The user-defined metadata may have been changed.
status	The purpose of this view is to set a new status (and a new creation time).
copy	The content of the source view is made accessible at a new location.
aggregate	The operator gathers the content of multiple source views.
technology	The operator is used to change the access model or methods for the data of the source view.
resource	The operator is used to change the resource mapping of a view.

The category *Permissions* declares who may use which operations on a view such as reading and writing data and/or reading metadata. How the data is represented and which methods are needed to access it is described by the category *Technology*. This information is used by verifying if the operating system at the target location (cf. category *Resource Mapping*) provides the requested mechanisms and to transparently convert the data if needed. The category *Resource Mapping* defines when and where the views content needs to be made accessible. Here the virtual infrastructure may be interfaced with SLA-based resource management mechanisms that support the *declarative* description of the delivered service level.

4.3 RUNTIME SYSTEM FOR MANAGING THE VIEWS

Scientists may work with the system via a graphical user interface (GUI) or a command line interface (CLI). Essentially, both interfaces offer the same functionality albeit their visual representation significantly differs. The interfaces are used to declaratively describe the views and observe the status of the virtual data infrastructure. The *Query* component enables the automatic retrieval of metadata for a data set specified by its URL in the category *Resource Mapping*. Hence, scientists may be relieved from repeated and cumbersome manual inputs of existing information. The *Identity Management System* provides information about the identity of users to which a scientist may wish to grant certain data access capabilities. This information – identities and capabilities – is attached to a view (category *Permissions*) and passed to the *Enactment* mod-

Figure 6: Components of the VISPA runtime implementing the views by interfacing the users and the resources.

ule to enable access to the data. All views are stored in the *View Description Store* (VDS). The components *Compiler/Adjustment*, *Enactment*, *Data Resource*, *Compute Resource* and *Monitoring* form a feedback loop that implements the declared virtual data infrastructure. The loop begins at the *Compiler/Adjustment* which obtains descriptions of views from the VDS and status information from the *Monitoring*. Next, the compiled data management operations are sent to the *Enactment* that interfaces with the resources. The results of these operations are monitored and fed into the *Compiler/Adjustment* to end one loop cycle. The feedback loop is similar to designs found in emerging flexible resource management frameworks that are based on Service Level Agreements (SLA) [7, 26].

EXAMPLE USES OF VIEWS

We demonstrate the use of views for recurring data management operations that are extracted from the case studies in Chapter 2.

5.1 INITIAL DATA REGISTRATION

Before any data may be managed by VISPA, it needs to be made known to the runtime system. This is done by *registering* existing data. Specific characteristics of such views are that they are not linked to source views (category *Provenance*) and the runtime system is only in charge of verifying if the data actually exists, but does not provision the data.

Because, views may be created at any level of abstraction (eg, single value, row or table in a database, a line of a file, a whole file, a set of files, file system, etc.), a user can register data at the most convenient interface. The only limitation is given by the capabilities of the runtime system that may only support specific types or abstraction levels of views.

Relation to Case Studies. In the presented case studies (cf. Chapter 2), convenient steps for initially registering data are: the selection of data sets in the CLUES scenario, the definition of configurations in the parameter sweep study, and downloads of data sets from the PANGAEA portal. Note, registering data as early in the data analysis as possible avoids losing metadata.

Declarative Description. The scientist describes the original data source (category *Metadata/User*) by specifying arbitrary metadata provided as key-value pairs. If the repository storing the data already maintains metadata, it may be automatically retrieved by the VISPA runtime. Additionally, a URL and a access time specification is needed to retrieve the data for subsequent processing (category *Resource Mapping*). Depending on the capabilities of the storage interface for accessing the data, information on the access model and methods is provided by the scientist, the data management operators or may be obtained by the VISPA runtime automatically. The latter may be enabled by the storage interface that could attach a MIME header to a response for an access request (ie, similar to HEAD and GET requests in HTTP). Last, information to authorize access to the data may be given or obtained automatically by the VISPA runtime.

Assuming that most of the information may be retrieved automatically by the VISPA runtime, a scientist merely has to specify a URL to access the data set plus some additional metadata that could capture information on the specific reason for creating an initial view.

Even if the information may not be retrieved automatically, it may already be available and easily obtainable (PANGAEA), extracted from data to be analyzed (CLUES) or given by the parameter set (PSS).

Once all descriptive data has been collected, it is handed over to the *View Description Store* (cf. Figure 6) which calculates the view's unique identifier, sets the creation time and puts the view into the state declared.

5.2 DATA COPY

We distinguish two main causes for copying data: (1) creating just another instance at the same resource (eg, for later manipulation and not compromising the original data), and (2) using the same data at another resource (eg, for processing the data). Copying data may easily be automated by declaring *which* data needs to be copied, and to *where* the data needs to be copied. Essentially, this operation creates a local or remote replica of the data. Scientists do this all the time struggling to keep track of where their data resides, what version the data is, and, last, but not least, what the best method for actually copying the data is (best wrt. used API and performance).

There are many examples for copying data in the case studies (cf. Chapter 2):

Use Case	Steps/Components Copying Data
CLUES	①, ②, ③, ⑤, ⑦ and ⑩
PSS	②, ③, ⑦ and ⑧
AWI	①, ②, ③, ④, ⑤, ⑥ and ⑦

Note, because the AWI use case resembles a rather generic model for organizing storage spaces and access to them, every component may be involved in copying data.

Declarative Description. A copy of a view is simply defined by instantiating a new view, specifying the identifier of its source view (category *Provenance*) and declaring at which resource the view needs to be provisioned (category *Resource Mapping*). The scientist neither needs to know what access methods must be used for retrieving the data from the source view nor what tools are required for uploading the data to the target resource nor when the data operation needs to be scheduled to ensure access during the desired time periods.

Because the VISPA runtime only enacts necessary data operations, declaring a view to be a copy of another may result in no data operation if the data at the target resource already exists. Particularly, this behavior is useful for creating a comprehensive virtual data infrastructure for existing data sets. Hence, metadata may be added a posteriori.

5.3 DATA ACCESS PERMISSIONS

Often scientists from different administrative domains perform joint research and need to exchange data. Data exchange is simple if the data is already published for public access or if the scientists are members of the same virtual organization (VO) (eg, employing a Grid infrastructure in the Digital Humanities [25] or using the *group* file space in the AWI use case). Otherwise, data is often exchanged via intermediate services (eg, the FTP server in the AWI use case). Implementing data exchange requires the scientists to manage the necessary data operations manually, create accounts for external partners to access the data, and clean up the storage space.

All these operations are needed for enabling access to data sets. Instead of performing these cumbersome operations manually, a scientist might simply

declare who may access the data, at which resource and during which time period.

Declarative Description. Granting access to data for a specific user or group of users may be declared by simply creating a copy of a view and adding corresponding capabilities to the category *Permissions*. Additionally, the view may be made available at a specific resource and for a limited period of time which is declared in the category *Resource Mapping*. Then, the VISPA runtime must provision the data at the resource and set the access permissions accordingly.

5.4 DATA TRANSFORMATION

Similar to copying data, transformations account for a vast number of operations. Such operations may be executed immediately time-sharing compute resources or processed by a batch system that allocates resources for exclusive use. In the case studies (cf. Chapter 2), examples of data transformations are:

Use Case	Steps/Components Transforming Data
CLUES	all blocks in box "Preparation of simulations", block GADGET (high res) and all blocks in box "Post-processing"
PSS	①, ④, ⑤, ⑥ and ⑨

Because the AWI use case described in Section 2.3 does not explicitly mention any data processing, we left it out here.

In fact, data transformations may be seen as operations that copy data and change it using some *user-defined function*. Whether the VISPA runtime triggers the execution of the transformation or not, depends on the state of the storage resource. If the data already exists, the view just declares metadata for a previously performed transformation. Note, if the container for the results (eg, a directory or a table) already exists and the results' individual URLs are not known a priori, the scientists need to enforce the execution of the data transformation.

Declarative Description. A data transformation view is declared by specifying its source(s) (category *Provenance*), a user-defined function (UDF) (category *Content*) that operates on the specified source(s), the data model of the results (category *Technology*), and a target resource for storing the results (category *Resource Mapping*). The specification of the UDF includes their parameters.

Note, it is assumed that the UDF may be executed in the context of the source view(s). That is, it may operate on, for example, a single file, a directory, single table or database, whatever is specified by the source view(s). A UDF, however, does not necessarily specify at which resource it must be executed. This decision may be left open to the VISPA runtime. Therefore, a UDF specification may include information to instantiate the user-defined function. In practice, the UDF could be specified by a job script that is represented by another view and by a resource broker or even an SLA that executes the job. Then the VISPA runtime needs to determine how it can provision the input data to the job and how it makes the data at the desired target resource available.

Additionally, the scientist may specify metadata that describes the transformation and the resulting content (category *Metadata/User*), and grant access to other scientists (category *Permissions*).

CONCLUSION

Scientists are faced with an overwhelming amount and complexity of both data and technologies to advance research. Additionally, state-of-the-art environments are distributed world-wide to share resources and facilitate collaborations. We found that existing solutions for storing and processing scientific data are limited to their specific scope. Leaving that scope – for employing emerging technologies or simply for collaborating with “external” partners – scientists are required to manually perform most data management operations themselves. Additionally, metadata is often only available within but not across a domain, hindering validating or reusing scientific results.

In this paper, we presented an approach for relieving the scientists from the burden of manual data management and let them concentrate on the best ways to make use of their data. The key idea of the presented framework is to structure data in **views** which are **declaratively** described. Then, the VISPA runtime compiles necessary data management operations, enacts them and observes the results of their execution.

Our next step is to develop a prototype and validate the conceptual framework.

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